

A Multi-Layered Natural Language Processing (NLP) Framework for Detecting Hate Speech in Online Forums.

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Abstract

This study proposes a multi-layered transformer-based Natural Language Processing (NLP) architecture for detecting explicit and implicit hate speech. Traditional single-stream transformer models may process input as a single block of text, potentially missing nuances derived from discourse-level or pragmatic context. By designing a multi-layered architecture, we hypothesize that the model will more accurately detect explicit hate and better capture implicit hate through rules and context modeling.

In this study we recommend a multi-layered framework consisting of a keyword and rule-based filtering layer, a Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) classifier, and a semantic similarity and embeddings layer.

Evaluation metrics utilised include precision, recall, and F1-score for explicit and implicit categories separately. The multi-layered rule and transformer-based model is expected to outperform standard single-layer or monolithic transformer models in detecting both explicit and implicit hate speech in online forums.

Keywords: Hate Speech, Natural Language Processing, NLP, Multi Layered, Transformers

Introduction

Hate speech generally refers to language that attacks or demeans a certain group of people or person because of their race, religion, gender, political ideology, or other personal traits. According to Nockleby (2000), hate speech lacks a constant legal definition. However, hate speech can take the form of slurs, mocking or dehumanising language, or outright calls for exclusion and even violence on people (Anderson & Barnes, 2022). Essentially, while the definition of hate speech might vary based on the platform or circumstance, there is a common thread of hostility aimed at marginalised groups or persons (Gorenc, 2022).

Social media platforms have amplified the scale and speed hate speech (Uyheng et al., 2022). Unlike traditional media, online moderation and gatekeeping can be challenging and hate speech can be online for a while (Gagliardone et al., 2015). Hate Speech content can be disseminated to thousands of people in seconds or minutes. In some instances, online forums and communities designed for socialising and sharing ideas or engaging content are used to push inflammatory material to wider audiences. Additionally, the ease of anonymity lowers the barrier for people or groups to coordinate harassment or share extremist content without much fear of accountability (Ossa, 2024).

In other instances where moderation is operational, people adapt their language over time, often inventing coded terms to slip past moderation tool. As a result, hateful content still shows up in comment sections and discussion threads, which shows how persistent it can be.

The effects of hate speech are not limited to virtual platforms. There is evidence linking exposure to online hate with real psychological harm, higher stress levels, and even reduced participation in public life (Saha et al., 2019). Over time, repeated exposure normalises this rhetoric and lowers the social barriers against openly discriminatory ideas. In extreme instances, individuals or groups have gone on to carry out violent acts offline.

The effort to regulate hate speech can be complicated for both legal and technical reasons. Countries have different frameworks on how much they restrict hate speech .While some prioritise safety, others prioritise free expression or freedom of speech (Negi, 2024). Additionally, online platforms might enforce their policies inconsistently, which can mean censoring harmless content while still letting a lot of harmful speech slip through.

Technically, detecting hate speech can be challenging because it depends so much on context and culture (Aroyo et al., 2019), and the vocabulary changes constantly. Older approaches

relied mainly on surface level word cues but newer methods use machine learning models that can pick up on context and meaning (Lee et al., 2023).

Automated hate speech systems are far from perfect. They can inherit biases from the data they are trained on (Garrido-Muñoz et al., 2021), struggle when applied to new platforms, and are often outsmarted by users who deliberately tweak their language. The main challenge is getting good coverage and detecting most of the harmful content, without too many false positives that end up punishing innocent users.

This project fits into that broader effort. We propose a multi-layered approach to detecting hate speech across online community forums. By leveraging current advances in natural language processing and machine learning, the multiple layers in the proposed hate speech detection system offers a more effective and context aware hate speech content moderation.

Literature Review

Brief History of Hate Speech Detection Tools and Techniques

Hate speech detection techniques have continued to evolve over time (Punyajoy et al., 2023). Initial hate speech detection tools (in the early 2000s) largely focused on manual rule based tactics supported by human-created lexicons and keyword-based filtering systems. The methodology is unassuming: flag words, phrases or content that are considered offensive. However, this often failed to flag the nuanced and evolving nature of online hate speech.

The application of machine learning (ML) techniques in the mid-2000s marked a key development in the field (MacAvaney et al., 2019). Supervised learning procedures such as Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Naïve Bayes classifiers were used to flag hate speech based on annotated datasets. However, while these systems were able to capture explicit hate speech (e.g., direct slurs or derogatory terms) they still struggled with handling the complexity of online conversations from different sources.

The application of deep learning (DL) techniques brought about noteworthy advancements. In some instances, researchers used recurrent neural networks (RNNs), convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and more advanced transformers like BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) (Mnassri et al., 2022) to improve the accuracy of hate speech classification systems. These models had the ability to understand the contextual relationships between words, and addressed one of the crucial limitations of earlier techniques: detecting implicit or context-dependent hate speech.

Furthermore, the availability of large, annotated datasets like the "Hate Speech and Offensive Language Dataset" (Davidson et al., 2017) provided researchers the opportunity to design and train more refined models which have the ability to detect a broader range of hate speech type (explicit or implicit, including microaggressions and subtle, offensive stereotypes).

Contemporary Approaches to Hate Speech Detection.

In contemporary hate speech detection, several approaches are often utilised. These may include the integration of natural language processing (NLP), machine learning (ML), and deep learning (DL) models to detect hate speech content across different online platforms.

- **Deep Learning Models:** These models rely heavily on transformer based architectures, such as BERT, RoBERTa, and DistilBERT, which are pre-trained on large corpora of text. Subsequently, they are fine-tuned on specific hate speech datasets (Jahan et al., 2021). The models understand the contextual meaning of words and phrases, allowing for a more nuanced detection of hate speech. For instance, words like "*terrorist*" or "*criminal*" may not always be offensive. However, their connotation will change based on the context they appear in. The models are able to capture subtle cues from context which is an important aspects of effectively classifying online hate speech.
- **Contextual Embeddings:** Unlike traditional word embeddings like Word2Vec or GloVe, which assign fixed meanings to words, contextual embeddings allow the same word to have different meanings based on nearby or surrounding words. This is particularly important when detecting hate speech, because the context can help to determine whether a term is hateful or not.
- **Multilingual and Cross Lingual Models:** Another modern development is the use of multilingual models, such as mBERT or XLM-R (Sarracén, 2021), that allow hate speech detection systems to be effective across different languages across different regions. This is important because hate speech manifests in various forms across various languages (and cultures), thus detecting hate speech in languages other than English is an ongoing challenge in NLP research.
- **Fine Tuning and Transfer Learning:** There is a large amount of annotated hate speech data available in different repositories and transfer learning has gained prominence. Pre-trained models are fine-tuned on smaller, precise datasets, and this improves accuracy without the need for a massive amounts of labelled data. This makes it possible to create specialised models for detecting hate speech in various domains such as politics and religion.

Common Rules and Systems that Help to Detect Hate Speech in Online Communities

Many online communities employ automated systems, such as bots and rule-based systems, to flag and remove hate speech. These systems can be broadly categorised into two groups: rule based and machine learning based. Rule based systems leverage on predefined dictionaries that contain a list of offensive words or phrases. They also combine lexicons and pattern matching techniques to identify and filter hate speech. For instance, some social media

platforms have utilised extensive keyword filtering systems that can detect variations of common hate speech terms. However, these systems can be overly one dimensional, as they fail to detect subtle hate speech or hidden meanings through coded language.

Automated bots and moderators programmed to detect certain keywords and other behavioural pattern are also used to monitor online content. These bots might implement sentiment analysis techniques to determine if the comment is negative or harmful. While these bots are effective, they sometimes flag content wrongly (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2022).

Circumvention of Hate Speech Automated Detection Systems

One of the most significant challenges in the fight against hate speech is how individuals circumvent automated detection systems. Implicit hate speech (in which the intent is disguised through coded language or oblique references), is particularly difficult for bots to detect. This is often done by:

- **Using Special Characters and Unicode Substitutions:** For example, users may replace offensive words with special characters or use Unicode characters that look similar to the letters in the target word (Dionysiou & Athanasopoulos, 2021). This makes it harder for bots to identify the term. However, more advanced detection systems can recognise these variations through tokenisation techniques.
- **Acrostic Language and Homophones:** Users might rely on homophones (e.g., "u" for "you") or acrostic language, where the first letter of each word in a phrase spells out a hidden message. Bots designed to focus on word matching will fail to catch this type of circumvention (Alonso et al., 2024).
- **Image and Video based Hate Speech:** Hate speech is no longer restricted to text alone. Users now turn to images, and videos to communicate harmful messages (Schmid et al., 2022). Bots and automated systems that rely solely on text analysis miss these multimodal forms of hate speech
- **Circumvention Strategies by Users:** Hate speech agents have become increasingly sophisticated in their tactics to avoid detection. For instance, users might employ “dog-whistle” tactics, where seemingly inoffensive phrases are used in contexts that signal to an in-group that the message is meant to be offensive. In such cases, detecting hate

speech requires understanding not just the words, but also the social/cultural context in which the words are used (Alonso et al., 2024).

In summary, hate speech can be propagated in different forms. It can be explicit or implicit, direct or indirect, and its detection often requires an understanding of the context in which it is used. The use of multi-layered systems that integrate different approaches such as keyword matching and contextual analysis are more proficient at handling this diversity. In the next section we outline a multi layered system that combines a keyword/rule based filtering layer, pre-trained language model (for contextual analysis), and semantic similarity and embeddings layer for identifying subtle hate speech patterns.

Methodology

Data Collection

Dataset for the project was curated using python libraries to retrieve relevant information and the extracted data was stored in CSV files. Specifically, data related to ten forum categories were extracted: business, celebrity, crime, education, food, health, jobs, politics, romance, sports.

While python script can be customised to extract specific data within a set time range (eliminating the need for expensive third-party tools), it is important to note that the data was extracted and warehoused in line with best practices. Additionally, sensitive data (such as personal/private information) were not collected in this project.

Data Pre Processing

Designing a solid data pre-processing and feature engineering pipeline is critical for building an effective Natural Language Processing (NLP) model for hate speech detection. In this project, each thread/post was reviewed to remove irrelevant symbols, links, special characters and personal identification data.

Data Annotation

Data annotation was implemented by a team of three (3) annotators for each thread using detailed guidelines. Clearly offensive or abusive comments were labelled as “*EXPLICIT_HATE*”, more subtle, but hostile offensive language targeted at individuals or groups were labelled as “*IMPLICIT_HATE*”. In instances where the language was ambiguous and the annotator was uncertain the thread was marked as “*UNSURE*” and escalated for further review. Lastly, posts/threads with non hate content was marked as “*NON_HATE*”.

Keyword and Rule Based Filtering Layer.

In this layer, we load the dataset from a csv file and implement rule-based patterns to classify text into different categories including: “*EXPLICIT_HATE*”, “*IMPLICIT_HATE*”, and “*NON_HATE*”. The rules in this layer flags explicit hate keywords in a list/dictionary grouped by category (racial, ethnic, religious, gender-based, homophobic, and Nigerian-context terms).

These are direct slurs or openly hostile language. If any of these terms appear as whole words in the text, the system flags the content as explicit hate. It also defines implicit hate rules (as regular expressions). The purpose of this layer is to provide a fast and interpretable first pass before advanced machine-learning layers are applied.

This layer and subsequent layers in the pipeline were designed using python scripts and libraries. The integrated development environment for executing the codes is Google Colabs.

Fine Tuned BERT Classifier Layer

In this layer we defined a BERT-based text classification system for detecting the classes hate speech: “*EXPLICIT_HATE*”, “*IMPLICIT_HATE*”, “*NON_HATE*” using PyTorch and Hugging Face Transformers.

The main class (*Layer2_BERTClassifier*) wraps the full pipeline including tokenization, training, evaluation, and prediction. Regarding the dataset handling, we implemented an inner *TextDataset* class which adapts tokenized text and labels to PyTorch’s dataset format so it can be used with *DataLoader*. A *_tokenize method* was utilised to convert raw text into BERT inputs (*input_ids*, *attention_mask*) with padding and truncation.

We also implemented a layer freezing strategy to freeze all BERT layers, then we selectively released the last N transformer layers (plus the classifier head). This enabled efficient fine-tuning while preserving pretrained knowledge.

During training, the model first filtered and encoded valid labels. Class weights are calculated to reduce the impact of class imbalance. Texts were tokenized and loaded into batches. An *AdamW optimizer* with different learning rates and a linear learning-rate scheduler was used to update parameters. The model was trained over multiple epochs with gradient clipping, and optional validation accuracy computed after each epoch.

Semantic Similarity and Embeddings Layer

In this layer, we defined a semantic similarity based classifier that works alongside earlier layers. Instead of training a classifier, it uses a pretrained *SentenceTransformer* model to convert text into dense vector embeddings that capture meaning. Its purpose is to judge how semantically similar new texts are to known examples in each category.

The *build_reference_embeddings* method was used to create embeddings for up to 500 example texts per category, storing them as tensors for efficient comparison. When analysing new input, the *analyze_similarity* method encoded each query text and computed cosine similarity between the query embedding and each category's reference embeddings. For each category, it keeps the highest similarity score, producing three similarity values per text. These scores represent how closely the text matches “*EXPLICIT_HATE*”, “*IMPLICIT_HATE*”, or “*NON_HATE*” language.

Multi-Layer Hate Speech Detection Pipeline

We designed a complete pipeline that combines the three different layers to classify text into “*EXPLICIT_HATE*”, “*IMPLICIT_HATE*”, or “*NON_HATE*”. The system is designed to be conservative, but inclusive by using simple rules first, then progressively implementing more complex models only when needed. The pipeline integrates pre-processing, rule-based filtering, machine learning, semantic similarity, and final decision logic into a single framework.

In the second layer, BERT produced predictions and confidence scores, focusing on learning subtle linguistic patterns that rule-based logic may miss. In the third layer, we applied semantic similarity using sentence embeddings. Finally, predictions from Layers 2 and 3 are combined using weighted voting (favouring BERT), producing a single final prediction with confidence and reasoning. The pipeline also includes methods for full-system evaluation and single-text testing, making it suitable for both research and practical deployment.

Predictions were made by comparing similarity scores against predefined thresholds and selecting the strongest category match. The pipeline also returns confidence score and similarity breakdowns, and human readable reasoning for transparency.

Results.

Evaluation Results

The system evaluation results indicate that the multi-layer system substantially improves performance beyond the initial filtering stage. While Layer 1 accuracy is very low (0.162), (suggesting weak coarse discrimination), the overall system achieves moderate accuracy (0.631) and F1-score (0.627), this shows that downstream processing meaningfully corrects earlier errors. Class-wise results reveal complementary behaviours in the system: “*EXPLICIT_HATE*” is detected with high recall (0.959) but moderate precision, (indicating aggressive detection), whereas “*IMPLICIT_HATE*” shows extremely high precision (0.974) but lower recall, reflecting conservative predictions. “*NON_HATE*” recall is relatively low, suggesting over-flagging of hate. Generally, the system favours sensitivity to hate speech at the cost of some false positives.

Classification Report			
Class	Precision	Recall	F1
<i>EXPLICIT_HATE</i>	0.480	0.959	0.640
<i>IMPLICIT_HATE</i>	0.974	0.514	0.673
<i>NON_HATE</i>	0.886	0.419	0.569
System Evaluation			
	Overall Accuracy	Overall F1-Score	Layer 1 Accuracy
	0.631	0.627	0.162

Table 1.0 Classification Report and System Evaluation

Layer	NON HATE	IMPLICIT HATE	EXPLICIT HATE	UNSURE
Prediction Distribution on Sample Data				
Layer 1 (Rules/Keyword)	--	0.8%	47.4%	51.8%
Prediction Distribution on Unsure Sample Data				
Layer 2 (BERT Classifier)	29.5%	21.2%	51.3%	--
Layer 3 (Semantic Similarity)	27.1%	40.8%	32.1%	--
Final Prediction Distribution on Sample Data				
All Layers	15.8%	17.6%	66.7%	--

Table 2.0 Prediction Distribution on Sample Data

Discussion

To improve the efficiency (speed/cost) and effectiveness (quality) of the entire system the first layer can be optimised to ensure it sends minimal noise downstream. The rules can be split into hard rules (to detect explicit slurs, with high confidence) and soft rules (for implicit slurs, with lower confidence). Confidence scores can be assigned to the rules as required. Negation handling can also be implemented. These implementations will reduce the number of false positives before the second layer. The second layer, which is a major decision engine should be optimised to handle challenges such as class imbalance, threshold sensitivity (tune class-specific thresholds), over detection and under recall of a particular class/category. If and when required, the system can use a binary first strategy (Hate/Non Hate) and distil hate classes into implicit/explicit classes in subsequent iterations.

This will improve class balance and stabilise predictions without increasing cost. In the third layer, cached sentence embeddings can be used for known patterns.

The system architecture can also be improved by adding early exit conditions (for example, high confidence rate for a class, stop early or skip the third layer), confidence level and rationale can be passed between layers. Monitoring and feedback features can be implemented to track layer rejection rates and class collapse warnings.

It is important that each layer should reduce uncertainty, not repeat work. In summary, Layer 1 should always be fast and conservative, Layer 2 should be precise and calibrated, and Layer 3 should be targeted and corrective.

Conclusion

In single-layered hate speech detection systems, the technique often relies on a single approach, such as keyword matching, sentiment analysis, or deep learning. However, they suffer from several limitations including

- **Context Limitation:** Simple keyword-based systems can easily be circumvented by changing or masking offensive terms. Single-layered systems that rely on sentiment analysis alone might miss instances where the tone is neutral or sarcastic, but the context is clearly hateful.
- **Lack of Nuance in Detection:** Hate speech can be explicit or implicit, direct or indirect, and its detection often requires an understanding of the context in which it is used. Multi-layered systems that integrate different approaches are more adept at handling this diversity.
- **Improved Accuracy:** Multi-layered systems combine multiple detection techniques to reduce the risk of false positives and false negatives. For instance, a first layer might flag text based on keyword matching, while a second layer could use deep learning to assess the context. This allows the system to be more accurate and less likely to overlook nuanced hate speech. We would like to recommend robust keyword dictionaries and optimised classifiers to attain high level accuracy.
- **Scalability:** Multi-layered systems are more scalable, as they can be trained to recognise various forms of hate speech across different domains and languages. They are also better at adapting to emerging forms of hate speech, which often evolve in response to changes in platform policies or detection mechanisms.
- **Human-in-the-loop Systems:** Some online platforms use a hybrid approach to monitor content. The use of human moderators (with bots) require the human in the loop to make a final decision on what constitutes hate speech. This methods provides flexibility for handling complex hate speech cases.

Recommendations

The multi layered system should be fine-tuned to address edge cases, use a broad keyword dictionary, and implement fine tune models trained on large datasets. Adding a human-in-the-loop layer also improves accuracy and ensures responsible, reliable decision-making.

Hate speech detection is an evolving field, and the challenges associated with detecting harmful content in online communities are far from being solved. While historical methods relied on simple, rule-based systems, modern techniques offer significant improvements in terms of accuracy and adaptability. However, as hate speech evolves and becomes more sophisticated, detection systems need to continue adapting, with multi-layered models offering the best promise for addressing both explicit and implicit hate speech effectively. The future of hate speech detection lies in the ability to combine automated systems with oversight, while also developing technologies that can catch subtler forms of harm, such as memes, images, and coded language.

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